

Strategy for the Development of the Indonesian Migrant Worker (PMI) Placement Program in the Formal Sector

Yeni Nuraeni¹, Suryadi²

^{1,2}Pusat Pengembangan Kebijakan, Kementerian Ketenagakerjaan, Jakarta, Indonesia
Email: yeninur@hotmail.com

Abstract

The Indonesian Government in 2011 carried out a moratorium with Middle Eastern countries to stop sending Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) to the informal sector. This moratorium was triggered by the many problems experienced by PMI, especially the informal sector, because they work for individuals, so that the guarantee of protection is minimal. With this moratorium, the Indonesian Government must upgrade the quality of PMI candidates to enter the formal sector where PMI has a working relationship with a legal entity company so that protection is guaranteed. This study aims to analyze & evaluate the extent to which the Government of Indonesia has made efforts to improve PMI placement programs in the formal sector and formulate a model for optimizing the role of related institutions. This study uses a qualitative analysis method with sampling using the purposive sampling technique. The sample of this study took two provinces in Central Java and East Java as the provinces that included the most PMI senders in Indonesia. The results show that to increase the placement of PMIs in the formal sector, there must be clarity of function and authority between institutions and ensure coordination between related institutions, activate the function of labor attachés and representatives of Indonesia to carry out Market Intelligence and encourage the use of market intelligence results as well as develop an integrated PMI information system.

Keywords: Indonesian Migrant Workers, PMI Placement in the Formal Sector, Employment Attaché Functions, Market Intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has an abundant workforce. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) recorded that the working-age population in Indonesia as of February 2020 was 199.4 million people. To create jobs for the workforce, it is necessary to accelerate economic growth (Sasongko & Huruta, 2019). The World Bank estimates that if the average economic growth in the 2013-2020 period is 6.5%, then around 12.4 million jobs will be created, while if it grows only at an average rate of 5% per year, then 10.2 million jobs will be created. This shows that there will be 2.2 million new jobs if economic growth can be accelerated from 5% to 6.5% in 8 years (Saez et al., 2021).

The analysis shows that there is still a large possibility of an increase in Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) in the next few years if economic growth slows down, resulting in more limited employment opportunities in the country (Olivia et al., 2020). Indonesia's economic growth until 2019 was only around 5%, and due to the pandemic in 2020, it reached minus 2.07, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Indonesia's Economic Growth Period 2011-2020

Source: (Minus 2020 Economic Growth, Lower Than Government Estimates, 2021)

Indonesia is currently the largest labor-sending country in the world. By looking at the workforce structure, which PMI still dominates with junior high school education and below, which is 63%, then the placement of PMIs, which mostly work in the household sector, may continue to take place (Shivakoti et al., 2021). Based on data from the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) in August 2021, the Government has placed 5,222 PMIs to work in several countries,

consisting of 71 percent or 3,710 people working in the informal sector and the remaining 29 percent or 1,512 people working in the formal sector (Lee et al., 2021). The PMI Placement data for 2021 can be seen in Figure 2.

PMI problems such as illegal placements, over-stayer work, and forced repatriation by the receiving country, as well as the death penalty, may still be on the Government's work agenda in the future related to the lack of protection of PMIs, especially those working in the informal sector (Djelantik, 2019). PMI dispatches, which are still dominated by educated and low-skilled personnel with job titles, mostly work as domestic workers, child caretakers/parents. Due to the nature of the work, by gender, the proportion of female PMI is higher than that of males (Fernandez-Reino et al., 2020).

Figure 2. PMI Placement Data for August 2021

Source: (BP2MI, 2021)

PMIs who work in the informal sector are prone to persecution, inhumane treatment, acts of violence, sexual harassment, murder, unpaid salaries and various other cases that often afflict PMIs, especially those who work in the informal sector (Vogt, 2013). This is because the government or PMI placement companies (P3MI) can't monitor PMI. While the cases in the formal sector are fewer than those in the informal, the Government and P3MI easily monitor the supervision procedures because they are not employed by individuals but by companies (Leerkes & Broeders, 2010). The government and PMI placement companies need to have good planning to get PMI candidates to enter the formal sector (Zwikael et al., 2019).

The Government has made various efforts to improve PMI's profile, such as increasing PMI's education, skills and competencies, and accelerating market intelligence implementation (Chofreh et al., 2020). The Government plans and predicts that one day there will be a time when there will be a tendency for hyperbolic placements, where placements in the formal sector are more than in the informal sector (Sengupta et al., 2021). For this reason, the Ministry of Manpower, together with the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) and other stakeholders, continue to make improvements on all fronts because sending PMI apart from reducing the unemployment burden and its domino effect in the country, has also provided a net value-added effect in the form of remittances that enter the country (Trinidad & Protacio-De Castro, 2020). PMI professionalism in the formal sector can significantly contribute to increasing the number of remittances. Meanwhile, remittances can positively impact the expansion of job opportunities and economic Development (Ramanayake & Wijetunga, 2018).

In Law Number 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers, it is regulated that the central and regional governments must protect all PMIs from before work, during work, to after-work (Husni & Cahyowati, 2020). The implementation of PMI Services, Placement and Protection involves a lot of government institutions, so it requires coordination and commitment, which does not seem to have materialized well in the field (Moretti, 2021). This can be observed among others; there is still uncertainty regarding the division of tasks between the central Government and local governments and clarity on who should coordinate all steps (Yang, 2020). This PMI Candidate affair involves many parties such as recruitment recommendations served by the Regency/City Manpower Office, Identity Cards served by the Ministry of Home Affairs, Health Checks by the Health Service, Passports by Immigration (Ministry of Law and Human Rights),

Validation of job orders and defense is served by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs through Indonesian representatives abroad, transportation by the Ministry of Transportation, security is served by the Police (recommendation letter from the police), training through the Overseas Job Training Center (BLKLN). BP2MI's role is to coordinate all work steps of these government agencies through the issuance of Overseas Manpower Cards (Ekowanti et al., 2020).

Based on the problems mentioned above, it is necessary to conduct research that aims to analyze & evaluate the extent of the efforts that have been made by related parties as well as coordination between Ministries and Institutions in the context of improving PMI placement programs in the Formal sector from the supply side (preparing TKI profiles related to education, skills, PMI competencies) and from the Demand side, (implementation of market intelligence, promotions, labor market information systems) as well as from the placement side. This study also aims to formulate a model for optimizing the role of relevant institutions in PMI placement programs in the formal sector.

Previous studies have discussed PMI placement in both the non-formal and informal sectors. In addition to having an impact on reducing the unemployment rate, the placement of PMI also contributes to remittances and can obtain a very useful source of foreign exchange. Remittances will have a micro impact if used for consumption investment and have a macro impact if used for productive investment (Hartiningsih, 2021). Factors supporting PMI placement include; good communication, the availability of adequate resources, strong commitment, and an efficient bureaucratic structure, while the inhibiting factors can be in the form of differences of opinion between implementers, lack of discipline in providing services and lack of understanding of the agents on regulations (Tawalare & Laishram, 2019). The lack of an active role from local governments, both provincial and district, has resulted in unclear case resolution patterns and coordination between local governments. To improve policy performance in providing services and protection for PMI, changes to the coordination pattern are an important need to be carried out immediately (Tevapitak & Helmsing, 2019). The Government can improve services and protection for PMI, including by focusing on protection at the time of pre-placement as a preventive effort to prevent the increase in PMI cases abroad (Busby, 2021). Regarding the use of a computerized system in PMI placement services, it can be concluded that using a computerized system affects the effectiveness of the PMI placement process. One of the factors that can increase the increase in the number of PMI deliveries to the formal sector is the tightening of the CPMI registration system from the job training stage to the use of the online system, which has been implemented since 2013 (Arner et al., 2018).

Previous studies generally only discussed certain parts of the PMI placement process in the informal sector and the formal sector. Likewise, the institutions' discussion is limited to a few institutions and does not discuss the overall involvement between ministries, institutions, and the private sector in the PMI delivery process (Volden & Andersen, 2018). The novelty of this research can be seen from the thorough discussion of the PMI placement process, both in terms of supply and demand. This research also tries to photograph the Ministries/Agencies and private parties involved in a unified PMI placement system. This study also limits the discussion to only PMI placement in the formal sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on Article 49 of Law No. 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers, there are three Implementers for the Placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers, namely; PMI Protection Agency (BP2MI), PMI Placement Companies (P3MI) and Indonesian Companies that have projects abroad (Shalihah, 2021). Most of the formal PMI placements are carried out through government-to-government cooperation schemes such as RI-South Korea in the fields of industry, manufacturing, agriculture, fisheries, and services, RI-Japan in the placement of PMI nurses and caregivers, and Republic of Indonesia-Timor Leste in the placement of midwives (Efendi et al., 2021). In addition, through the Indonesian Government's cooperation scheme with private parties abroad, such as the placement of female PMI in the electronics manufacturing sector in Penang, Malaysia, and private to private cooperation schemes, as has happened in many work sectors as well as formal PMI placements through P2MI (Hidayat & Virgianita, 2019).

PMI placement procedures have the same standards, which include; looking for information on job vacancies abroad, participating in counseling, registering and selecting, signing placement agreements, medical tests, getting job training and competency tests, obtaining passports, participating in PMI insurance, participating in PAP and signing work agreements, taking care of recommendations for fiscal-free last departure abroad with complete documents (Lin, 2018). After arriving at the destination country, PMI must report to the Embassy of the Republic of Indonesia. Then PMI can work following the work agreement by choosing a residence permit and work permit in the destination country (Yeoh et al., 2020). PMI must go through many stages, involving various government agencies and private parties who must be able to coordinate and collaborate to provide services and protection to PMI effectively and efficiently (Low, 2021).

With the enactment of Law no. 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers, there is a new paradigm in the protection mechanism for PMI. The implementation of PMI protection must be carried out in an

integrated manner by involving the Central Government, Regional Governments, the private sector and the community (Juddi et al., 2021). The PMI protection paradigm based on Law no. 18 of 2017 can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Paradigm Model of the Indonesian Migrant Worker Protection System according to Law Number 18 of 2017

Source: Bambang et al. (2018)

So that workers abroad can compete with workers from other countries, must pay attention to the quality of education and skills possessed by PMI candidates, especially in the formal sector and the need for cooperation by sitting at one table between the Government and P2MI and other relevant private institutions to resolve labor problems abroad. A quality PMI delivery policy implies that it can overcome employment problems and increase economic Development through remittances received from the workforce. Meanwhile, PMI will receive the same wages as workers from other countries with the same level of expertise and will improve the economy of individuals and families in their area of origin (Baird et al., 2018).

METHOD

This research is descriptive qualitative research that evaluates and analyses the Government's efforts to increase PMI placement in the formal sector. This study uses primary data and secondary data. Primary data collection techniques were carried out using in-depth interviews, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) methods, and observation. The secondary data was obtained through literature study and documentation.

The purposive sampling technique did the selection of research loci. The research location in East Java Province and Central Java Province as a sample considering that these two provinces are the largest PMI senders in Indonesia. The selected informants in this study came from relevant agencies related to policymaking related to PMI placement, namely, BPS (Central Bureau of Statistics), BP2MI, P3MI, Ministry of Manpower, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, BNSP, LSP, P2MI formal sector and other relevant agencies.

The data analysis technique used the descriptive qualitative analysis technique. The research framework can be seen in Figure 4:

Figure 3. Research Framework

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Formal Sector PMI Placement System

P3MI in Central and East Java provinces recruit many candidates for PMI in the Formal sector from high school graduates (Efendi et al., 2021). The PMI recruitment model for the formal sector is to collaborate with related parties, including:

1. With the Vocational high school party
 - To collect and organize alumni or prospective alumni to provide information about job opportunities abroad.
 - Together with the school providing counseling, assisting and escorting those interested in registering to complete the required document requirements.
2. Mass Media
 1. To promote P3MI companies and available job orders through promotions through electronic and print mass media including through brochures, banners or billboards, advertisements and newspapers, both daily and weekly, radio and local television advertisements, and direct outreach to the public.
3. UPT BP2MI
 2. By holding regular job fairs or job fairs with special events filled by P3MI to inform job seekers directly of opportunities to work overseas.

In practice, based on the results of interviews with informants from P3MI, the formal PMI placement process begins with the recruitment process for PMI candidates (CPMI) who mostly take from SMK graduates/alumni. CPMI from graduates/alumni from SMK is considered to have special skills already, so P3MI does not need to do any more training. The formal CPMI training and/or debriefing process will be carried out by companies/users from abroad and facilitated by P2MI. This training/debriefing process can occur domestically or at the user company's place abroad. The PMI placement system for the formal sector can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. PMI Placement System for the Formal Sector in Central Java

From the PMI placement chart in the Formal sector, a simple process flow for PMI placement can be described, including:

3. P3MI, after obtaining a Job Order from an Agency/Company Abroad, will submit a Permit of Deployment (SIP) to the Manpower and Transmigration Office of Central Java Province.
4. After obtaining a Permit for Recruitment/Recruitment, P3MI will receive a Recruitment Introduction Letter (SPR) from this permit. P3MI recruits through SMK, the recruitment process is carried out by promoting, among others, using brochures, advertisements on the radio, participating in job fairs, or visiting directly to SMK.
5. After obtaining the Prospective Manpower, P3MI will coordinate with BP2MI or UPT BP2MI to complete the administrative requirements. Then the Agency/user company will conduct a direct test regarding the feasibility and workability of the prospective TKI.
6. The PMI candidate will be dispatched after P3MI submits a Passport Recommendation Letter through the Prov/city/district Manpower Office if they pass the selection.
7. PMI candidates will receive a short training (debriefing) for 2-3 days regarding their duties and types of work.

The Role of P3MI, BLKLN & Mini Vocational Schools in the Formal PMI Placement Program

In East Java Province, there are P3MI and BLKLN, which place formal and informal TKI. According to data compiled from BP2MI until December 2020, there were 60 P3MI and 68 BLKLN until 2019. Meanwhile, in Central Java Province, there were 23 P3MI until 2020 and 92 BLKLN until 2010. There are P3MI which usually double as BLKLN, which are included in private educational institutions and take part in the formal PMI placement program. However, of the many existing BLKLN, they train more informal PMIs, because specifically for Formal PMI, in general, formal PMI candidates have passed the competency test and received competency certification. Candidates for formal PMI can leave without going through education and training. This happens because it is assumed that those in the formal sector already have their skills, so they don't need to be trained anymore.

In addition to BLKLN, specifically in East Java Province, there are also so-called mini SMKs included in private educational institutions that play a role in the formal PMI placement program. Mini Vocational School is one of the Governor of East Java programs, seeking to overcome the large number of workers who have not been absorbed in the world of work, especially those who are graduates of Islamic boarding schools in East Java Province. Through this program, because Islamic boarding schools already have their educational institutions, the East Java Regional Government assists various Islamic boarding schools (SMK Mini), of which 70% are training facilities and infrastructure, and 30% are in the form of entrepreneurship training in remote bases. "The term Mini Vocational School is intended to accommodate the development of existing vocational schools within the Islamic boarding school environment" (Maskuri & Minhaji, 2017). The purpose of the establishment of this mini SMK is that it is hoped that Islamic boarding schools can be involved in preparing their students to become students who are not only experts in the field of religion but are also skilled in the business and industrial world, so that the independence of their graduates will be formed to be ready to work in various business sectors, both formal and informal" (Maskuri & Minhaji, 2017).

Ideal Formal TKI Placement System Based on Inputs from Informants

According to various respondents found in the provinces of East Java and Central Java, the ideal formal sector PMI placement system is through the G to G (Government to Government) and G to P (Government to Private) mechanisms. In this system, the main requirement to become a formal sector PMI is to pass the administrative selection and pass a medical test, after which they will be given debriefing or final education and training. The G to G system is considered better considering a written agreement (MoU) between stakeholders. PMI placement by the Government is carried out based on a written agreement between the Republic of Indonesia and the Government of the user country (G to G) and the Republic of Indonesia with legal entity users (G to G P). With this agreement, the placement of PMI by the Government, which in this case is carried out by BP2PMI, guarantees the protection of PMI in the formal sector. In terms of legality, the regulations are clearer, so that it will also guarantee the business continuity of companies implementing PMI placements. In addition, from the perspective of PMI candidates, they will avoid problems if the completeness of the documents has been fulfilled.

The implementation of PMI placement in the formal sector G to G and G to P models faces various obstacles both on an international and national scale that can hinder developing the PMI placement program in the Formal sector. The main obstacles faced today are, among others, the existence of price competition between overseas representative agents or commonly referred to as Field Officers (PL)/sponsors. However, the existence of PL/sponsors does not always have a negative impact. In fact, sometimes sponsors' presence is very helpful and needed, especially for PMIs who are working abroad for the first time so that the migration process can run smoothly (I. Chandra & Atom, 2011; Sri, 2017).

Other obstacles faced in developing a national PMI placement program include the lack of clarity in coordination between government agencies in the regions, such as the coordination line for reporting formal PMI data between the Provincial Manpower and Transmigration Population Office and the Provincial UPT BP2PMI. Meanwhile, in terms of P3MI, it is still difficult to get recruits based on job orders received from overseas agencies because for the Central Java Province, the largest portion of P3MI recruits is still from Vocational High School (SMK) graduates. The difficulties experienced by P3MI are more of a non-technical nature, such as convincing the parents of prospective PMI in the Formal sector who come from SMK graduates.

Meanwhile, international constraints in terms of several job orders such as requests for Butcher (Animal Slaughterer / Butcher) from Canada require requirements that are too difficult in terms of foreign language competence which is quite high TOEFL requirement with a score of 750.

PMI Formal Sector Job Market

The more PMIs work in the formal sector, the better the protection side. It will also raise the image of Indonesia abroad, that PMI does not only work as assistants, but many also work as professionals in their fields that require high skills. The Government can make various efforts through upskilling and upgrading PMI and increasing the number of PMI placements in the formal sector abroad.

Workers from Indonesia, especially the formal sector, are quite popular abroad. So far, the types of vacancies and job opportunities for PMIs in the formal sector are available in various placement countries, including construction, oil, mining, transportation, services, hospitality and tourism, nurses, supermarket waiters, plantation workers, agriculture and fisheries. Based on data from BP2PMI, there are five priority sectors of employment for the formal sector PMI, namely; Health: Kuwait, Qatar, Taiwan, UAE, Japan, Hospitality: Singapore, Macau, UAE, Bahrain, Oil and Gas: Qatar, Australia, Kuwait, Qatar, Malaysia, Construction: Macau, Malaysia. Opportunities for PMI placement as nurses are wide open. The United States, Australia, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Qatar, United Arab Emirates (UAE), Japan, and Taiwan desperately need nurses from Indonesia (Mujiati et al., 2020).

Several countries in Eastern Europe, such as Czechoslovakia and Russia, asked for many workers from Indonesia to work there, especially as health massage workers in spas and therapists. PMI employment opportunities in Eastern Europe for this field are relatively new, following the large number of workers in Eastern Europe absorbed by Western Europe and the United States, so that these countries began to look for workers to the Asian region. In addition to Eastern Europe, the absorption of formal PMI for the Middle East region is also quite large, to be placed in the construction, mechanics, and petroleum engineering sectors.

It is necessary to continue to strive and be encouraged so that PMIs have skills, work competencies and work professionalism to fill formal job vacancies available abroad. Employment opportunities in the formal sector available in the international job market are still wide open for PMIs. However, to fill job opportunities in the formal sector, the quality of PMI must be optimally improved through job training. Relevant Government and private institutions must continue to strive to develop the expansion of the labor market for Indonesian migrant workers and continue to realize the placement

of PMI in the formal sector in line with the strategic plan to eliminate PMI for domestic workers (PLRT). The Government needs to widen the variety of agreements for placement of professional PMI in many areas of work and industry through the strategy of Increasing Cooperation & Diplomacy and Integration of data access & administration (Widiyahseno et al., 2017).

According to the Presidential Instruction, sending PMI to the formal sector is prioritized over the non-formal sector. P3MI is asked to open more job opportunities for PMI in the formal sector abroad. It is hoped that P3MI can expand its network to companies in placement countries to find job vacancies for PMI in the formal sector.

PMI Job Market Information System

Managing data on migrant workers, employment agencies, employer and destination country policies and labor market information represents an important aspect of protection and empowerment. In Indonesia, APJATI has started to set up an electronic data center for all migrant workers it sends along with labor service agents and employers in the destination country (Lindquist, 2018). However, government agencies should act as leaders to ensure that the information is independent and accurate. This is illustrated in the Migrant Worker Placement and Protection Law, which states that the Government has the responsibility "to establish and develop an information system for the placement of prospective Indonesian workers to work abroad." The law does not define how the information system should be built and maintained or the purpose of managing such data.

Law No. 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PPMI) explains the information that migrant workers have the right to obtain, such as the job market, procedures for placement and working conditions abroad, as for the families of migrant workers, it is important to obtain information about the conditions, problems, and the return of their family members who work in the country of placement (Ady, 2019). BP2MI pioneered the Development of the Overseas Job Market Information Service, known as SISKOTKLN or the Computerized System for Overseas Workers, which is a data collection system for Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers who will go abroad. In the process, SISKOTKLN involves various parties related to PMI placement, including Regency/City Offices, P3MI, Overseas Job Training Centers, Health Facilities, Insurance, Psychological Examinations, Competency Testing Institutions, Financial Institutions, and Indonesian Representatives abroad. In the future, this information system is expected to be developed into an integrated information system that contains information on supply and demand for the foreign job market.

There are still many weaknesses from the SISKOTKLN application system, which is now running, including; Supply information that has not been entered into the application, so SISKOTKLN can only display from the demand side, especially job vacancies in the formal sector. SISKOTKLN has not been integrated between related institutions and between central and regional governments. To improve the performance of the SISKOTKLN application, improvements must still be made, including by increasing the relevance, accuracy, productivity, adaptability and completeness of the facilities in SISKOTKLN to increase user satisfaction (Asep, 2015).

Strategy for Improving the PMI Placement Program in the Formal Sector

The availability of job opportunities for formal PMI abroad must be met with the readiness and availability of PMI candidates who have the skills and competencies following the needs of the labor market. BP2MI launched two strategies in expanding the PMI job market, namely opening up job opportunities in the formal sector and increasing skills and abilities for Indonesian citizens who did not receive high school/vocational education. The two strategies are expected to help PMI meet the high demand because Indonesian workers are friendly and tenacious but do not have the required skills and abilities.

Some of the strategies for improving the formal TKI placement program are as follows; increasing the placement of PMI in the formal sector with policies by design (prepared early and planned), not by accident (when there is a new demand looking for workers), increasing the implementation of market intelligence and roadshows to various potential countries, upskilling, upgrading, adjustment training (link, train, and match), encourage increasing the role of BLKLN, LPK, LKS, BNSP, LSP to be more proactive in preparing PMI candidates for the formal sector following the required competency standards, multilateral and bilateral diplomacy, in collaboration with domestic centers of excellence (universities, polytechnics, vocational high schools, job training centers and so on), develop a migrant labor market information system, especially the formal sector that is integrated and socialized on its use.

To increase PMI placement in the formal sector, cross-sectoral collaboration is needed. It is necessary to formulate a strategy to optimize institutions that have a dominant role in PMI placement in the formal sector. The Ministry of Manpower has a dominant role in improving the BLKLN program for the placement of PMIs in the formal sector, improving the performance of P3MI, developing information on the overseas job market/Job Fair, and increasing collaboration with private LPKs and professional associations. BP2MI, as the institution that runs the operations of PMI placement in the formal sector, has a dominant role concerning; providing incentives in the process of placing PMI in the Formal sector, encouraging the placement of G to G/P for PMI in the formal sector, developing a formal PMI job market application

system that contains information on supply and demand in an integrated cross-sectoral manner and is integrated between the central and regional governments.

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs role is no less important in encouraging the PMI placement program in the formal sector, including those related to efforts, facilitating bilateral, regional and multilateral meetings, increasing the effectiveness of implementing market intelligence on the PMI formal sector job market. The Manpower Attache under the command of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs has roles related to the placement of PMI in the formal sector, including; identifying existing opportunities as well as open access and networks to facilitate the entry of Indonesian migrant workers into the formal sector, prepare the quality of the workforce in collaboration with the Directorate General of Development, Vocational Training and Productivity at the Ministry of Manpower. In terms of promotion, the Ministry of Trade has a role in promoting formal PMI placements through the Free Trade Agreement/Economic Partnership Agreement (services).

To increase the competence of PMI candidates, P3MI has a crucial role concerning efforts to; improve the quality of training for formal sector PMI candidates, improve their BLKLN, increase collaboration with government and private educational institutions and training institutions for the placement of formal sector PMIs. Meanwhile, to strive for PMI candidates to have the competencies required by user countries, the role of BNSP is to produce PMI candidates who have internationally recognized competencies. The dominant roles of BNSP include; reduce the gap between the demand and the availability of PMI in the formal sector in terms of competence and language, improving the implementation of competency tests and certification for educational and training institutions that provide candidates for formal PMI as well as revamp the competency standards compiled through the SKKNI.

To improve the PMI placement program in the formal sector, it is necessary to build an integrated system through a coordination mechanism between related institutions, both government and non-government institutions, in carrying out their respective functions, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Integration of PMI Placement Development Programs in the Formal Sector

CONCLUSION

There is still a lack of clarity on the division of legal authority between state institutions at the national, provincial and district levels. This results in a very minimal level of coordination and cooperation or duplication of work between government agencies in carrying out their functions related to the formal PMI placement program. The level of education and skills of formal PMI candidates is still low, making it difficult to meet the competencies required by users, so the Government needs to improve the competencies of formal PMI candidates so that they can compete in the global job market. The unavailability of an accurate and integrated formal labor market information system to match supply and demand.

To improve the efficiency and effectiveness of services and protection of PMI in the formal sector, various improvements still need to be made, including; there must be clarity of function and authority between institutions and ensure coordination between institutions, activate the function of the labor attaché and representatives of the Republic of Indonesia to carry out Market Intelligence and encourage the use of market intelligence results, Development of an integrated migrant worker information system and socialization of its use.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ady, T. DA. (2019). *Kemener Luncurkan Aplikasi Sistem Informasi Buruh Migran*. Retrieved from <https://m.hukumonline.com/berita/baca/lt5c2f93ede529b/kemener-luncurkan-aplikasi-sistem-informasi-buruh-migran?page=all>
- [2]. Arner, D. W., Buckley, R. P., & Zetzsche, D. A. (2018). Fintech for financial inclusion: A framework for digital financial transformation. *UNSW Law Research Paper*, (18-87).
- [3]. Asep, H. (2015). *Pengaruh Penerapan Sistem Komputerisasi Tenaga Kerja Luar Negeri Terhadap Efektivitas Kerja Dalam Penempatan Tenaga Kerja Luar Negeri*. Universitas Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa.
- [4]. Baird, S., McKenzie, D., & Özler, B. (2018). The effects of cash transfers on adult labor market outcomes. *IZA Journal of Development and Migration*, 8(1), 1-20.
- [5]. Bambang, W., Rudianto, & Ida, W. (2018). Paradigma Baru Model Pelindungan Pekerja Migran Indonesia Dalam Perspektif Undang-Undang RI Nomor 18 Tahun 2017. *Sosio Informa*, 4(3).
- [6]. BP2MI. (2021). *Data Penempatan dan Pelindungan PMI Periode Agustus 2021*.
- [7]. Busby, J. W. (2021). Beyond internal conflict: The emergent practice of climate security. *Journal of Peace Research*, 58(1), 186-194.
- [8]. Chofreh, A. G., Goni, F. A., Klemeš, J. J., Malik, M. N., & Khan, H. H. (2020). Development of guidelines for the implementation of sustainable enterprise resource planning systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 244, 118655.
- [9]. Djelantik, S. (2019). The Indonesian Women Migrant Workers: Redefinition and Termination of Sending Them Abroad. *International Relations*, 7(04), 139-149.
- [10]. Efendi, F., Haryanto, J., Indarwati, R., Kuswanto, H., Ulfiana, E., Has, E. M. M. A., & Chong, M. C. (2021). Going Global: Insights of Indonesian Policymakers on International Migration of Nurses. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 14, 3285.
- [11]. Efendi, F., Oda, H., Kurniati, A., Hadjo, S. S., Nadatien, I., & Ritonga, I. L. (2021). Determinants of nursing students' intention to migrate overseas to work and implications for sustainability: The case of Indonesian students. *Nursing & Health Sciences*, 23(1), 103-112.
- [12]. Ekowanti, M. R. L., Bustami, M. R., & Raharja, W. T. (2020). Institutional Strategic Management of Manpower Planning in Nusantara Malay Archipelago:(Case Study on Indonesia's Public Policy of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) Working in Malaysia). *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 7(4), 168-191.
- [13]. Fernández-Reino, M., Sumption, M., & Vargas-Silva, C. (2020). From low-skilled to key workers: the implications of emergencies for immigration policy. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 36(Supplement_1), S382-S396.
- [14]. Hartiningsih, T. (2021). The Impact of the Moratorium Policy on the Sending of Indonesian Migrant Workers and Remittances in Indonesia in 2010-2019. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 27(6), 1-8.
- [15]. Hidayat, A., & Virgianita, A. (2019). Technical assistance for innovation development from and to developing country: Case study of Indonesia's foreign aid to Timor-Leste. *International Journal of Development Issues*.
- [16]. Husni, L., & Cahyowati, R. R. (2020). Legal Protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers Based on Law Number 18 of 2017. *Journal of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Issues*, 23, 1-6.
- [17]. I.Chandra, A., & Atom, G. M. (2011). *Profil Pengalaman TKI : Pemberangkatan, Di Luar Negeri dan Kepulangan*.
- [18]. Juddi, M. F., Perbawasari, S., & Zubair, F. (2021). The Communication Flow in the Protection of Indonesian Female Migrant Workers through the Migrant Worker Family Community (KKBM). *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 22(5), 19-37.
- [19]. Lee, B., Ibrahim, S. A., & Zhang, T. (2021). Mobile Apps Leveraged in the COVID-19 Pandemic in East and South-East Asia: Review and Content Analysis. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 9(11), e32093.

- [20]. Lin, C. (2018). Weak taxation and constraints of the welfare state in democratized Taiwan. *Japanese Journal of Political Science*, 19(3), 397-416.
- [21]. Lindquist, J. (2018). Reassembling Indonesian migration: biometric technology and the licensing of informal labour brokers. *Ethnos*, 83(5), 832-849.
- [22]. Low, C. C. (2021). Digitalization of Migration Management in Malaysia: Privatization and the Role of Immigration Service Providers. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 1-29.
- [23]. Maskuri, & Minhaji. (2017). Analisis Kebijakan Pemerintahan Daerah Jawa Timur Tentang Pengembangan SMK Mini di Pondok Pesantren. *JPII*, 1(251-272).
- [24]. Moretti, S. (2021). Contested regionalism in the Asia-Pacific: the case of the Bali Process and the protection of refugees. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 1-18.
- [25]. Mujiati, Amir, S., Sri, M. N., & Rosita. (2020). Penempatan Perawat pada Fasilitas Pelayanan Kesehatan di Luar Negeri: Alur dan Kendala. *Jurnal Penelitian Dan Pengembangan Pelayanan Kesehatan*, 4(1), 39-50.
- [26]. Olivia, S., Gibson, J., & Nasrudin, R. A. (2020). Indonesia in the Time of Covid-19. *Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies*, 56(2), 143-174.
- [27]. *Pertumbuhan Ekonomi 2020 Minus, Lebih Rendah dari Perkiraan Pemerintah*. (2021). Studiekonomi.Com. <https://studiekonomi.com/nasional/pertumbuhan-ekonomi-2020-minus-lebih-rendah-dari-perkiraan-pemerintah/>
- [28]. Ramanayake, S. S., & Wijetunga, C. S. (2018). Sri Lanka's labour migration trends, remittances and economic growth. *South Asia Research*, 38(3_suppl), 61S-81S.
- [29]. Saez, E., Schoefer, B., & Seim, D. (2021). Hysteresis from employer subsidies. *Journal of Public Economics*, 200, 104459.
- [30]. Sasongko, G., & Huruta, A. D. (2019). The causality between inflation and unemployment: the Indonesian evidence. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 20, 1-10.
- [31]. Shalihah, F., Agusmidah, A., & Wijayanti, A. (2021). Effectiveness of one-stop integrated services in optimizing the role of Indonesian migrant workers protection agency in Central Java. *Linguistics and Culture Review*, 5(S3), 1099-1110.
- [32]. Shivakoti, R., Henderson, S., & Withers, M. (2021). The migration ban policy cycle: a comparative analysis of restrictions on the emigration of women domestic workers. *Comparative Migration Studies*, 9(1), 1-18.
- [33]. Sri, M. (2017). Kedudukan Petugas Lapangan Di Pelaksana Penempatan Tenaga Kerja Indonesia Swasta (Pptkis) Dalam Perekrutan Calon Tenaga Kerja Indonesia (Studi Pada Pptkis Di Kota Mataram). *Jurnal Ilmiah Fakultas Hukum UNRAM*, 1-15.
- [34]. Tawalare, A., & Laishram, B. (2019). Factors hindering effective partnering in Indian public sector construction organizations. *Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction*.
- [35]. Tevapitak, K., & Helmsing, A. B. (2019). The interaction between local governments and stakeholders in environmental management: The case of water pollution by SMEs in Thailand. *Journal of environmental management*, 247, 840-848.
- [36]. Trinidad, A. C., & Protacio-De Castro, E. (2020). The institutionalization of mental health and psychosocial support in emergencies in Indonesia. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 51, 101918.
- [37]. Volden, G. H., & Andersen, B. (2018). The hierarchy of public project governance frameworks: An empirical study of principles and practices in Norwegian ministries and agencies. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*.
- [38]. Widiyahseno, B., Rudianto, & Widaningrum, I. (2017). Paradigma Baru Model Pelindungan Pekerja Migran Indonesia Dalam Perspektif Undang-Undang RI Nomor 18 Tahun 2017. *Sosio Informa*, 4(3), 501- 513.
- [39]. Yang, K. (2020). Unprecedented challenges, familiar paradoxes: COVID-19 and governance in a new normal state of risks. *Public Administration Review*, 80(4), 657-664.
- [40]. Zwikael, O., Meredith, J. R., & Smyrk, J. (2019). The responsibilities of the project owner in benefits realization. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.